

Polymer/Solid Interfaces Through Multi-scale Simulations

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SUMMARY

The study of polymer nanocomposites at the molecular level is an emerging research area. Here we present results concerning chain mobility in polymer/solid interfaces, obtained through a hierarchical multi-scale simulation approach. Atomistic and coarse-grained dynamic simulations allow us to study a broad range of length and time scales.

Keywords: polymer dynamics, polymer/solid interfaces, multi-scale simulations

POLYMER/INORGANIC INTERFACES

Introduction

Polymer melt/solid and polymer melt/vacuum interfaces are encountered in many technologies involving adhesives, coatings, lubricants, and composite materials, where adsorbed molecules control the overall performance of the multiphase material system [1]. Today, such interfaces play a key role also in new applications involving hybrid materials where nanoparticles are added to polymer to alter its structural and mechanical properties without affecting the main chemical features of the supporting matrix.

In applications involving polymer/inorganic interfaces, in addition to the polymer/substrate interaction energy, knowledge of polymer mobility in the film (and how it is altered by the presence of the boundary) is absolutely necessary for controlling the wetting or friction properties of the interfacial system. In literature there is a vast number of experimental works study the polymer dynamics of interfacial systems [1-5]. However, there exist significant differences in the findings of the works as far as the length scale of the phenomenon and the extent of the surface effect on the lateral motion of the chain are concerned. Developing simulation tools that establish a link between these properties and the chemical constitution of the material and its interatomic interactions is therefore highly desirable: through the construction of a hierarchy of tools that span all relevant length scales (from the atomistic to the mesoscopic to the macroscopic), one can understand structure-property-processing-performance relations in the composite or hybrid structure and develop principles for optimal process and product design.

Atomistic detailed molecular simulations provide a very useful tool for understanding the structure-property relations of various materials [6,7]. Application of these

techniques to multi-component nanocomposites, however, is not straight forward due to the broad range of length and time scales characterizing them. For this reason simulation methods at different lengths and time scales needed. Here we present a hierarchical multi-scale multi-time approach that combines dynamic simulations from different levels of description. The methodology consists of two stages. The first one concerns detailed atomistic Monte Carlo (MC) and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of polymer/solid interfaces, whereas in the second stage coarse grained (CG) dynamic simulations are performed.

Atomistic Simulations of Polymer/Inorganic Interfaces

Recently we have presented a hierarchical simulation approach for the simulation of polymer/solid and polymer/vacuum interfaces that combines atomistic MC and MD simulations [8,9]. Model polyethylene (PE) melts adsorbed on a graphite phase and exposed to vacuum on the other side has been simulated using state-of-the-art atomistic simulation techniques. Figure 1a shows a snapshot of PE/graphite model systems. The local structure and conformation at the PE melt/graphite and PE melt/vacuum interfaces, was studied and results were presented for the mass density, conformation tensor, torsion angle distribution and bond-order parameters in the film as a function of distance from the graphite phase. The conformations of adsorbed polymer chains and their distribution in trains, tails and loops were also analyzed and compared to available data. The work reported here addresses the issue of molecular mobility at the two interfaces. We are interested in both the short-time (local) dynamics of the melt and the long-time (diffusive) motion of adsorbed segments or entire chains in the polymer matrix.

Figure 1: (a) Polymer/solid interface at the molecular level, (b) polymer density profile

Results are presented for the structure and the dynamics of linear PE melts adsorbed on a graphite phase and exposed to vacuum on the other side from detailed atomistic MD simulations in the NPT statistical ensemble at $T = 450$ K and $P = 0$ atm. Various polymer/solid systems were studied with molecular lengths ranging between C_{40} to C_{400} . The MD simulations were carried out, using a multiple time step algorithm [6], for times up to 100 ns to reliably calculate the transport properties of the adsorbed films.

More details about the polymer model and the polymer/graphite interaction can be found elsewhere [8,9].

Figure 1b presents the density profile $\rho = \rho(z)$ characterizing a 200-chain C_{78} melt; strong PE structuring is indicated in the figure up to approximately 18 Å from the substrate. Beyond 18 Å, the profile assumes an asymptotic form characteristic of a system with a constant local mass density, equal to that of bulk PE, up to positions where the free surface of the melt is encountered (at the melt/vacuum interface). The melt free surface is depleted in polymer mass and the density profile attains the characteristic sigmoidal shape, dropping gradually from the bulk value to zero at the extreme edge of the film. Motivated by the oscillatory structure of the density profile, the interfacial area can be divided into five (5) distinct “zones” or “regions”, using as guides the minima of the local mass density distribution (dashed lines in Figure 1a).

Dynamics of Polymers Near Solid Inorganic Interfaces

Conformational relaxation at the PE melt/graphite and PE melt/vacuum interfaces is quantified through the time decay of the torsional autocorrelation function (TACF), defined as:

$$P(\phi(t)) = \frac{\langle \cos \phi(t) \cos \phi(0) \rangle - \langle \cos \phi(0) \rangle^2}{\langle \cos \phi(0) \cos \phi(0) \rangle - \langle \cos \phi(0) \rangle^2},$$

where the brackets denote an ensemble average over all torsional angles $\phi(t)$. $P(\phi(t))$ for a polymer/graphene system (length of polymer C_{156}) for atoms belonging to each of the five regions defined in Figure 1b is shown in Figure 2. It is found to that in region I (which coincides with the first adsorption layer in the density profile), local dynamics is considerably slower than in the bulk while in regions II, III, and IV of the film, torsional dynamics is indistinguishable from that observed in the unconstrained bulk polymer system of the same molecular weight, M . Finally at the free surface of the melt (region V), local dynamics is considerable faster than in the bulk.

Figure 2: Torsional time autocorrelation function for a polymer/graphite system and its spatial dependence. With circles are results from bulk polymer MD simulations.

The long-time diffusion coefficient of adsorbed segments normal to graphite has been calculated by mapping MD trajectories onto the solution of a macroscopic diffusion equation. Extracted self diffusion coefficients are reported as a function of film thickness; their dependence on chain length is also discussed.

Overall, the methodology of calculating the transport properties of the simulated adsorbed films (i.e., the diffusion constant D) in the z direction normal to graphite involves the following steps:

- (a) First *long* MD simulations are performed, with a model PE/graphite system whose thickness is large enough to ensure the existence of a true bulk-like region in all aspects (thermodynamic, structural, conformational and dynamic). The 200-chain C_{78} /graphite melt with $L_z = 240 \text{ \AA}$ ($\approx 17 R_g$) considered here is such a system.
- (b) Then L_z is divided in N_b bins (of thickness $dz = 5 \text{ \AA}$ each) and initial ($t = 0$) distribution of tagged atoms, $f(z)$ is defined, such that the selected population of “tagged” segments included all carbon atoms belonging to a region of the interfacial film extending up to a distance d from the graphite plane ($z = 0$). In a further step the MD trajectory is analyzed and the corresponding concentration profiles $C_{MD}(z_i, t)$ ($i=1, 2, \dots, N_b$) of “tagged” atoms at all subsequent times ($t > 0$) are calculated.
- (c) Finally the diffusion coefficient D is estimated through minimization of the objective function F defined according to:

$$F(D) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_b} [C_{diff}(z_i, t; D) - C_{MD}(z_i, t)]^2 ,$$

where $C_{diff}(z, t; D)$ is the concentration profile calculated numerically [9], for a given value of the diffusivity D .

Figure 3: Diffusion coefficient, D , of adsorbed segments as a function of the thickness d of the film from the graphite plane and how it changes with time.

A unique feature of the new approach is its capability to characterize segmental mobility as a function of the width or thickness d of the chosen interfacial region segments belonged to at the beginning of the diffusive process, by properly choosing $f(z)$. For example, by defining $f(z)$ to include first only the carbon atoms of the 1st adsorption layer (by choosing $d = 6 \text{ \AA}$) and then the carbon atoms of both the 1st and 2nd adsorption layers (by choosing $d = 11 \text{ \AA}$), one can investigate whether or not segmental mobilities in the two layers differ and to what extent.

Figure 3 shows the diffusion coefficient (scaled with the bulk diffusion coefficient) as a function of both time and distance from the solid surface. Obviously D depends strongly on the thickness d of the layer next to graphite they lie at the beginning of diffusion: the closest the layer to the graphite plane (i.e., the smaller the value of d), the slower the segmental mobility. It is seen that d must be at least 90 \AA , i.e., $6-7 R_g$, for the diffusion coefficient D in the C_{78} PE film to be equal to that in the bulk C_{78} melt. Experimental studies with other polymer melt/solid surface systems have proposed totally different values for such a distance, ranging from $3-4 R_g$ [3] to $25 R_g$ [4].

HIERARCHICAL MULTI-SCALE SIMULATIONS

The results presented above concerns detailed atomistic simulations of polymer/inorganic systems with rather small molecular weight of the polymer matrix, i.e. for thick polymer/substrate systems only polymers with molecular length up to C_{78} were studied. As mentioned in the Introduction, to study multi-component nanocomposites with higher molecular weight, simulation methods at different levels of description needed. Here we present the second stage of our hierarchical methodology, which combines dynamic simulations at the atomistic and the CG description. With the proposed approach CG simulations can be directly used for quantitatively predicting the dynamics of high molecular weight polymeric systems. The method involves atomistic and CG MD simulations in some reference systems and allows us to define correctly the time scale in the CG runs [10-12].

Coarse-grained (CG) Molecular Dynamics Simulations

The CG simulations have been developed directly from the chemistry. Such models provide a clear way for connecting the atomistic-microscopic and the CG-mesoscopic scale and also allow the quantitative prediction of the polymeric properties using CG mesoscopic simulations. In more detail, groups of chemically connected atoms are lumped into 'superatoms'. The direct link to the chemistry, in structure-based CG models, is maintained through effective bonded and non-bonded temperature dependent potentials (more precisely free energies), which are obtained by averaging over microscopic details of the underlying atomistic models. As a test case we discuss in details an application of this hierarchical approach to polystyrene (PS) [10]. The whole systematic procedure to develop CG models using information from the atomistic level can be summarized in the following steps:

- 1) First, atomistic molecular dynamics (MD) or Monte Carlo simulations of isolated random walks are performed.

2) Then histograms of bonded distributions, $P^{CG}(x)$, with x being bond length, bond angle and dihedral angle, are sampled by collecting a large number of independent conformations for each PS random walk at a given temperature T . The standard assumption that the probability distribution function can be factorized is used. This is only valid if the internal CG degrees of freedom are uncorrelated. For our CG PS model this has been checked carefully by choosing properly the CG mapping scheme.

3) Having the independent probability distributions, the coarse-grained bonded potentials are given from the inverse Boltzmann relations, i.e. $U^{CG}(x) = -k_B T \ln(P^{CG}(x))$. Finally, the mesoscopic force field has to be completed by adding a suitable non-bonded interaction potential. Typical choices are Lennard-Jones-type potentials with heuristically modified exponents, or similarly modified WCA potentials (purely repulsive). This depends on the system and the intended use of the model.

Figure 4: Coarse-graining mapping scheme of PS: one monomer is mapped to two different CG beads ($\sigma_A=4.1\text{\AA}$, $m_A=27\text{amu}$ and $\sigma_B=5.2\text{\AA}$, $m_B=77\text{amu}$. CG bonds are shown with dash lines.

CG MD simulations have been performed using a CG model for PS in which one PS monomer is mapped onto two effective coarse grained beads, i.e. a 2:1 model (see Figure 4). CG bead "A" corresponds to the CH_2 of a PS monomer plus the half mass of each of the two neighboring CH groups along the chain backbone, whereas CG bead "B" is the phenyl ring [10]. This model does not lose too many structural details in comparison to all atom systems, while still being very efficient compared to atomistic simulations. Various monodisperse atactic PS melts, with molecular weight from 1.000 g/mol up to 50.000 g/mol have been studied with CG MD simulations. Note that the characteristic molecular weight M_e for the formation of entanglements for atactic PS is about 15.000 g/mol (at $T=463\text{K}$) [14].

The capability of the CG simulations to predict the polymer structure and the polymer dimensions has been examined by comparing the results with data obtained from atomistic simulations and experiments. Finally a systematic way to back-mapping the CG configurations onto the atomistic level has also been developed [10].

Quantitative Prediction of Dynamic Properties Through CG MD Simulations

In a second stage, dynamical properties of long entangled PS melts are studied with CG MD simulations [11-12]. In the literature usually CG models have been used for the

qualitative study of the polymer dynamics and the prediction of the universal behavior (“power laws”). Only recently, through the systematic development of CG models using information from the atomistic level, it has been allowed to investigate quantitatively the dynamical behavior of polymeric systems. The methodology consists of the following steps: First the dynamics of the CG PS melts has been compared with detailed atomistic data by using a proper time mapping scaling parameter, $S(M)$, based on results of short PS chains. The parameter $S(M)$ has been computed, and found to be consistent, using data from translational (mean square displacements of chain center-of-mass and of segments) as well as orientational (autocorrelation function of the end-to-end vector) dynamics. By doing this, the time in the CG description can be defined accurately and the CG simulations can be used to provide quantitative information about the polymer dynamics. The plateau value of S can be used for scaling the CG dynamic results of longer polymeric chains, where it is not possible to have reliable atomistic data [12]. Thus, we are able to calculate dynamical properties of high molecular weight entangled PS melts and to compare directly with experimental data.

Systems with molecular weight up to 50.000 g/mol are simulated and the polymer chain self-diffusion coefficient is calculated [12]. With the proper time mapping, we present, *quantitative* predictions of polymer chain diffusion using CG simulations *without any adjustable parameter*. Furthermore both simulation and experimental data show, after correcting for the chain end free volume, a clear transition regime from Rouse to reptation-like behavior [12,13]. The molecular weight for the crossover from Rouse to reptation like behavior, both from experimental and CG diffusion data is around 25000-30000 g/mol.

Figure 5: Diffusion coefficient, D , of polymer chains obtained from the CG simulations (open symbols) compared to experimental data [14].

Figure 5 shows diffusion coefficient of long entangled polymer melts (with molecular weight up to 50.000 g/mol) obtained from the CG simulations and compared directly to experimental data [12,14]. The results show a remarkable qualitative and quantitative agreement between the experimental and the simulated diffusion coefficients. This is of particular importance considering that results from the CG dynamic simulations are compared to experimental data, by using only detailed atomistic simulations for a few

reference short-chain systems. Furthermore, the dynamics at the segmental level has also been studied, by monitoring local bond time correlation functions and compared to nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) experiments. The very good agreement between the CG and the experimental data clearly shows that our CG model, which is still close to the chemistry, can directly used predict relaxation modes of bond vectors with characteristic times of only about 0.1-1ns up to the diffusion of the whole chain. This simultaneous prediction of two different dynamical modes, i.e. translational (mean square displacement of beads) and segmental orientational (bond decorrelation) dynamics, can be used to predict dynamical quantities obtained from different experimental techniques.

The length and time scales involved in the dynamics of the polymer systems studied through the proposed multi-scale multi-time approach vary over a very broad range: On the one hand the segmental relaxation on length scales of about 0.5nm (length of the “A-B” bond) corresponds to times of about 0.1-1ns. On the other hand the end-to-end vector of the higher molecular weight PS chains (50kDa) is about 14nm, and their diffusion coefficient of the order of about $10^{-11}\text{cm}^2/\text{sec}$ (at $T=463\text{K}$). This results into a relaxation time of the whole chain, ie. decorrelation of the end-to-end vector, τ_d (according to reptation theory $\tau_d = \langle R^2 \rangle / 3\pi^2 D$ [13]) of about 6.0ms. The broad spectrum of length and time scales studied here is about 3-4 orders of magnitude beyond that what can be modeled with atomistic molecular dynamic simulations. Furthermore the direct study of such scales from a *single dynamical run* is also a characteristic of the proposed methodology, to be distinguished from coarser models. A key point in the proposed methodology is that the CG model is still close to the chemistry. Thus CG simulations can describe properly all the length scales only above about 0.5-1nm and time above a few hundreds of ps. Furthermore the multi-scale nature of the proposed scheme, combined with a back-mapping procedure [10], allows studying time scales *ranging from a few fs up to ms* (about 12 orders of magnitude) by MD simulations and to compare directly to or predict experimental data without any adjustable parameter.

Current work involves the combination of the methodology presented above to study realistic polymer/inorganic interfaces at a very broad range of length and time scales. Such interfaces are representatives of carbon nanotubes nanocomposites. In overall the combined simulation approach open up the ways to model realistic polymer/clay nanocomposites directly from the molecular level. Finally, the proposed computational approach is very general and can be directly extended to other polymer chemistries by properly choosing a structure-based CG model, which reproduces structural properties for length scales of about 0.5-1nm and larger.

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